

CYBERLENINKA

BASE

OpenAIRE

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SHARQ FALSAFASI CERTIFICATE

OF PARTICIPATION

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

Xonturayeva Sayxuna

THE ROLE OF BORROWED WORDS IN CREATING

CROSS – CULTURAL COMMUNICATION AND UNDERSTANDING

DRJI

Universal
Impact Factor

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